

Fully Integrated On-Chip Inductors: An Overview

Róbert Ondica

Institute of Electronics and Photonics
Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
robert.ondica@stuba.sk

Richard Ravasz

Institute of Electronics and Photonics
Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
richard.ravasz@stuba.sk

Adam Hudec

Institute of Electronics and Photonics
Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
adam.hudec@stuba.sk

Martin Kováč

Institute of Electronics and Photonics
Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
martin_kovac@stuba.sk

David Maljar

Institute of Electronics and Photonics
Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
david.maljar@stuba.sk

Viera Stopjaková

Institute of Electronics and Photonics
Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
viera.stopjakova@stuba.sk

Abstract—This paper presents an overview and State-of-the-Art of fully integrated inductors with common fabrication processes used for implementation of these structures into a chip. The first step is an overview of fabrication technologies that starts with standard CMOS general purpose processes expanded by Far-BEOL and substrate alteration process (SOI, Silicon Embedded, TSV, TGV, PTH, Core Insertion); and continues to advanced process nodes like SMMT and Bond Wire utilization. Then, an overview of fully integrated inductor structures consists of selected topologies with notable parameters achieved in last few years. Critical parameters of integrated inductors include: inductance L_{DC} , inductance density L_A , quality factor Q , self-resonant frequency FSR and series resistance R_{DC} . These parameters are as important as the purpose and fabrication process.

Index Terms—Fully Integrated Inductor, Integrated Passive Device (IPD), Air Core Inductor (ACI), Silicon Embedded Inductor (SEI), Magnetic Core Inductor (MCI)

I. INTRODUCTION

Expanding market with electronic devices calls for more complex circuits occupying less area. Moore's law (and its modifications e.g. [1], [2]) is still present in today's design of integrated circuits. This does not apply only to higher integration density of transistors but also to other devices on a chip. With decreasing area for design of integrated passive devices (IPDs), it is necessary to consider new special layout approaches or new fabrication processes. These processes can be specifically developed for creating custom IPD with specific properties, however, utilizing a standard general purpose

inexpensive technology is vital for high volume semiconductor manufacturing processes.

TABLE I: Alphabetical list of used abbreviations

ACI	Air Core Inductor
BEOL	Back End of Line
CMOS	Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor
EPL	Equal Path Lengths
eSiFO	Embedded Silicon Fan-Out
FBEOL	Far-BEOL
FEOL	Front End of Line
FOWLP	Fan-Out Wafer Level Packaging
GP	General Purpose
IC	Integrated Circuit
IPD	Integrated Passive Device
MCI	Magnetic Core Inductor
MEMS	Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems
MEOL	Mid End of Line
PGS	Patterned Ground Shield
PTH	Plated Through Holes
SEI	Silicon Embedded Inductor
SMMT	Silicon Molded Metal Transfer
SOI	Silicon on Insulator
TGV	Through Glass Via
TSV	Through Silicon Via

An on-chip inductor with satisfactory properties is still considerably challenging task but research and commercial sector have come a long way within recent years with integration of inductors while achieving interesting results. To authors best knowledge, this paper presents the best results achieved lately in full integration of inductors. With emphasis on increased inductance L_{DC} , inductance density L_A , quality factor Q , self-resonant frequency FSR and reduction of series resistance R_{DC} , we performed a comparison of State-of-the-Art integrated inductors. While the comparison is based on many numerical (L_{DC} , L_A , Q , FSR , R_{DC}) and some non-numerical properties (technology, purpose), it is not our aim to select one best structure but to identify a relative value of each property of inductors to each other. Technology process and purpose of inductors are tightly tied with the final electrical properties of each structure and represent a determining factor of inductor suitability.

This paper is organized as follows: Section II describes inductor as a general purpose device. Section III briefly describes fabrication processes used for manufacturing IPDs and ICs, in general. Section IV summarizes and compares the best achieved results in integration of inductors in last years. Last section concludes the performed overview of manufacturing techniques and comparison of fully integrated inductors.

II. INDUCTOR

Inductor is a passive, two-terminal electrical component capable of storing energy in its own magnetic field when an alternating electric current flows through it. Each conductor has its own inductive properties and creates a magnetic field around itself, but its intensity is mostly negligible. In order to improve the inductive properties, inductor is formed by a conductor that is turned several times around a common center. The center of inductor is called the core and it can be made of magnetic or non-magnetic material [3]. The core also affects the inductance and other properties of inductors [4]. For example, in work [5], insertion of a magnetic core into solenoid inductor caused improvement of Inductance and Quality Factor 27.8 times and 5.2 times, respectively.

Shape of the inductor also affects its performance [6]–[10]. Common shapes of integrated inductors are following:

- Stripline [9], [11], [12],
- Circle Spiral [10], [13],
- Rectangle [9], [10], [14]–[20],
- Octagon [9], [10], [21]–[23],
- 8-Shaped [8], [24],
- Toroid [25]–[27],
- Solenoid [4], [5], [10], [28]–[36]

III. FABRICATION PROCESS

Fabrication process of the whole chip is tightly connected to properties of designed circuit/system as well as every single component. Standard manufacturing process of integrated circuit (IC) consists of front-end of line (FEOL), mid-end of line (MEOL) and back-end of line (BEOL) process steps:

- FEOL - first steps of chip manufacturing process where substrate is present without layers, patterns and exposed metal areas [37],
- MEOL - manufacturing of metal-based gate structures and self-aligned contacts with the first metal layer interconnecting such structures [37],
- BEOL - the final steps of process, when the conductive interconnections between on-chip devices are added [37].

Integration of inductor is often linked with more complex additional process steps, which can be excessively intricate and expensive to become high volume semiconductor manufacturing processes.

This paper considers only selected fabrication processes which has been used to manufacture a fully integrated inductor in recent years. Processes are not limited to inductor manufacturing but can be used for manufacturing of any IPD or for other purposes.

A. Standard General Purpose Technologies

Utilizing a standard General Purpose (GP) CMOS technology without any Post-CMOS process steps is usually less expensive approach than other special technologies but it is not suitable for inductor integration due to the absence of thick low-resistivity metal layers or magnetic materials in standard BEOL processes. However, these processes are wide-used, well documented and without significant process variations. With utilizing special layout techniques (e.g. Horizontal Parallelization [38], Slicing [39], Tapering [40], Equal Path Lengths (EPL) [41], Patterned Ground Shield (PGS) [42], [43] and others), the inductor properties can be optimized to comply with requirements in these technologies as well [8], [20], [22]–[24]. These techniques can effectively suppress undesirable parasitic effects present in on-chip inductors caused mostly by high frequency signal (e.g. skin effect, eddy currents, parasitic capacitances, etc.).

B. FBEOL

FBEOL, Far-BEOL or Far back-end of line is method of forming a patterned layer over a BEOL stack by deposition of new layers. New layers can be patterned and can have openings for through layer interconnection similar to standard BEOL processes. Its main purpose is protection and encapsulation of manufactured chips [44]. By deposition of conductive materials in combination with insulating and magnetic layers, fully-integrated inductor with magnetic cores can be formed on top of IC with decent inductance density $L_A = 133$ nH/mm², quality factor $Q = 16$ at frequency $F = 3.2$ MHz [5], [35].

C. Silicon on Insulator

Silicon on Insulator (SOI) technology is manufacturing process for creation of integrated devices on high resistivity substrates. Higher resistivity decreases energy losses in substrate caused by parasitic capacitance between devices and silicon substrate [45]. This process can significantly reduce

substrate losses and improve the performance of integrated devices [43], [46].

D. Embedded Silicon Fan-Out

Another type of a silicon embedded inductor can be created by utilizing embedded Silicon Fan-Out (eSiFO) process [14], [15] that is proposed as alternative to Fan-Out Wafer Level Packaging (FOWLP). This process is more simple without molding, temporary bonding and de-bonding steps but adds more process steps before FEOL process [47].

E. Core Insertion

Insertion of magnetic core during manufacturing of integrated inductors can lead to immensely high inductance $L_{DC} = 1\,063$ nH and inductance density $L_A = 354.3$ nH/mm². In this case, a created structure has rather low quality factor $Q = 1.3$ [4]. Process node is based on deep silicon etching and copper electroplating to create Silicon Embedded Inductor (SEI) MCI using 15 process steps.

F. Magnetic Alloy Deposition

Enhancement of inductor properties can be done by magnetic material addition not necessarily in core of the inductor. Deposition of magnetic materials on the surface of metal paths reportedly increases inductance of the whole structure.

Integrated rectangle inductors with deposited permalloy rectangle patterns ($11\ \mu\text{m} \times 13\ \mu\text{m}$) of three different values of thickness (20 nm, 60 nm, 92 nm) were reported with the maximum value of quality factor $Q = 11$ at $F = 6\,500$ MHz and inductance densities up to $L_A = 19.3$ nH/mm² [16].

Embedding the whole inductor in magnetic material was studied in [48]. With emphasis on different shapes of magnetic laminations for Stripline inductors, interesting results were achieved: quality factor up to $Q = 10.1$ at $F = 60$ MHz and inductance densities up to $L_A = 41.7$ nH/mm² [12].

G. Through-Silicon-Via

Through-Silicon-Via (TSV) is conductive connection between top and bottom sides of a silicon wafer created by deep etching of substrate and subsequent deposition of conductive materials into the formed trenches. It is electrically insulated from other TSV connections and the substrate [49]. With subsequent deposition of other conductive materials on top or bottom of substrate, it is possible to create connections or devices. For example, one can create a SEI by one-side etching [50] or both-side silicon substrate etching to form a double-side integrated SEI [17], [51].

With further alteration of this process, there are derived approaches that can be used for integration of inductors. Relatively simple modification of this process is to replace the substrate material with a high-resistivity material to suppress parasitic capacitance between inductor and substrate [18]. Glass substrate was also used to create integrated inductors with extremely high value of quality factor: $Q = 150$ at frequency of 4.5 MHz with relatively high inductance density $L_A = 66.5$ nH/mm². Through Glass Via (TGV) fabrication

process has also proven to be scalable, high reliable and potentially can achieve a high yield [28]. In combination with a magnetic core, also high value of inductance $L = 250$ nH ($L_A = 261.3$ nH/mm²) with the quality factor around $Q = 17$ at frequency $F = 20$ MHz can be achieved in this technology [52].

Plated-Trough-Holes (PTH) is another TSV process alteration, where TSV holes are plated with a magnetic material in order to create Coax Magnetic Core Inductor (MCI) [32]. In this case, potentially only two process steps are added to enhance electrical properties of IPDs comparing to TSV technology.

H. Silicon Molded Metal Transfer process

Silicon Molded Metal Transfer process (SMMT) creates structure electrically insulated from substrate and other on-chip devices by air gap while connected to an IC by copper bumps. Firstly, a structure is created in one substrate presenting the mold by a process similar to TSV. Subsequently, the structure is released from the mold, and is connected to IC on another substrate [53]. High inductance density $L_A = 171.9$ nH/mm² ACI with the maximum quality factor $Q = 22$ at relatively low frequency $F = 3.4$ MHz was achieved using SMMT process already in 2015 [18].

I. Bond Wire Inductor

Bond wires are essential parts of IC packaging. They are used to connect circuits integrated on a chip to the package frame, thus connecting IC to external circuitry. The essential parameter of a bond wire is its parasitic inductance that elevates more significantly with frequency and should be considered during the circuit-level simulations [54], [55]. On the other hand, the inductance of bond wires can be useful for manufacturing of integrated inductors [56], [57].

IV. OVERVIEW

As noted before, there is no simple straightforward comparison view of two structures of fully integrated inductors. Direct comparison of inductors electrical properties with ignoring the technological process of the structure fabrication or its intended purpose could be highly misleading. For example, the maximum quality factor of inductor applied in RF circuits should be at higher frequencies (> 1 GHz) as well as self-resonant frequency FSR . The same properties would not be useful for an inductor designed for voltage regulators working within the frequency range from ones to hundreds of MHz.

On the other hand, series resistance R_{DC} causes the power dissipation in inductor structure and it is important to keep it as low as possible. It is also crucial to increase inductance density L_A of on-chip inductors because of the tight area possibilities and cost reduction purposes.

Comparison of selected inductor structures is shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2. Figure 1 shows comparison of series resistance R_{DC} and inductance density L_A . Inductance density values of selected inductors are from ones to hundreds of nH/mm² and series parasitic resistance value is within the

Fig. 1: Comparison of R_{DC} and L_A parameter of fully integrated inductors

Fig. 2: Comparison of the maximum quality factor Q_{max} and frequency $F_{Q_{max}}$ of fully integrated inductors

range from tens of $m\Omega$ to hundreds of Ω . The graph indicates that with increase of inductance density, the series resistance increase can be observed as well.

Figure 2 shows comparison of the maximum quality factor Q_{max} and frequency at the maximum quality factor $F_{Q_{max}}$. The highest values of quality factor of these inductors are in the range from ones to tens at frequency values from ones of MHz to tens of GHz. One can also observe that by utilizing magnetic materials into the inductor structure (core or surface coating) the maximum quality factor can shift to lower frequencies.

Table II summarizes key parameters of the selected on-chip inductors implemented and published within the last 4 years. Inductors were fully integrated and evaluated by measurements except for structures in [8], [23] and [24]. These three structures were evaluated only by simulation but achieved interesting results in standard general purpose cost effective technologies without any post-CMOS process steps, where achieved values of inductance densities were $L_A = 150.6$ nH/mm², $L_A = 32.292$ nH/mm² and $L_A = 24.015$ nH/mm², and the maximum quality factor (Q_{max}) values of 15.6, 3.1 and 6 were reported.

Advanced technologies tend to be more expensive but on the other hand, there is possibility to achieve extremely high

inductance $L = 1\ 063$ nH as well as inductance density $L_A = 354.3$ nH/mm² (as reported in [4]) manufactured by inserting magnetic core into the inductor structure for power Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS) devices. Similarly, high value of quality factor $Q = 30$ was achieved for on-chip inductor manufactured in a standard 180 nm CMOS technology by using advanced materials for the inductor structure with inductance density $L_A = 39.68$ nH/mm² [58]. Other structures worth mentioning are a solenoid inductor with high value of quality factor ($Q = 150$) at frequency of 4.5 MHz and also with relatively high value of inductance density $L_A = 66.5$ nH/mm² manufactured using advanced TGV process for a RF filter [28], and a fully integrated square-shaped coupled inductors with $Q = 10.5$ at frequency of 7 000 MHz and with $L_A = 32.3$ nH/mm² that was manufactured in a standard rather low-cost 180 nm CMOS technology for application in a class-D LC oscillator [23].

V. CONCLUSION

This paper brings an overview of achieved results in IPDs integration in different fabrication processes. With emphasis on full integration of inductor, the manufacturing processes are briefly described. This state-of-the-art overview can be useful introduction to manufacturing processes of IPDs and also integrated circuits in general. Mentioned fabrication processes are standard GP technologies, FBEOL, SOI, TSV, TGV, PTH, eSiFO, SMMT and fabrications based on deep silicon etching and depositions of metallic structures. Fully integrated inductors, which have been manufactured in last years with the best electrical properties (e.i. high values of L_{DC} , L_A , Q , FSR and low value of R_{DC}) were summarized and compared here. Comparison of structures is not aimed at choosing one best structure but rather to compare possibilities in implementation of inductors for different purposes and manufactured by different fabrication processes. The performed analysis and presented overview of on-chip inductors might be very useful not only for IC research and development purposes but also in education and teaching, where curricula of different subjects on integrated circuit design can be complemented.

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TABLE II: State-of-the-Art of fully integrated inductors within years 2018 - 2022

Parameter	Unit	2018 [9]	2018 [25]	2019 [12]	2019 [4]				
Technology	[-]	130nm SiGe BiCMOS	TSV	Magnetic Alloy Deposition	Deep Si Etching + Cu Electroplating				
L_{DC}	[nH]	0.135	85	6.1 ³	7.33	73.3	1063		
R_{DC}	[mΩ]	-	0.23	-	-	-	149.6		
Q_{max}	[-]	21.73	14.3	10.1 ³	8.5 ³	37.6	14.7		
$F_{Q_{max}}$	[MHz]	68 000	12.5	30 ³	50 ³	21	14.1		
FSR	[GHz]	173	194	-	-	-	-		
Area	[mm ²]	0.003	5.6	0.146	0.5	4	3		
Shape	[-]	Rectangle	Octagon	Toroid	Stripline	Solenoid	Solenoid		
Special Note	[-]	-	SEI MCI	Magnetic Laminations	SEI MCI	SEI MCI	SEI MCI		
Number of Turns	[-]	1	25	-	5	20	15		
L_A	[nH/mm ²]	42.871	15.179	38.988	37.62	14.7	21.7		
							354.3		
Parameter	Unit	2019 [19]	2020 [24] ¹	2020 [14], [15]	2020 [26]	2020 [13]	2020 [5]	2020 [34]	2021 [8] ¹
Technology	[-]	-	180nm CMOS ²	eSiFO	-	SMMT	FBEOl	-	65nm CMOS ²
L_{DC}	[nH]	2.5	6 ³	2.5	57.5	25	120	3.9	0.223
R_{DC}	[mΩ]	47	-	5.1	16	121	270	39	-
Q_{max}	[-]	7.798	14 ³	1.2	11.65	31 ³	16	15 ³	15.6
$F_{Q_{max}}$	[MHz]	70	3500 ³	500	1	120 ³	30	100 ³	37500 ³
FSR	[GHz]	-	17.2 ³	-	-	-	0.4 ³	-	92 ³
Area	[mm ²]	0.69	0.25	1.5	3.06	2.67	1	0.5	0.008 ³
Shape	[-]	Rectangle	8-Shaped	Rectangle	Toroid	Circle	Solenoid	Solenoid	8-Shaped
Special Note	[-]	In Package	-	SEI Coupled	MCI	Suspended	MCI	MCI	-
Number of Turns	[-]	3	3	1	-	3.5	19.5	-	2
L_A	[nH/mm ²]	3.584	24.015	1.667	18.791	9.362	120	7.8	37
									150.6
Parameter	Unit	2021 [16]	2021 [32]	2021 [17]	2021 [23] ¹	2022 [52]	2022 [58] ¹		
Technology	[-]	Magnetic Alloy Deposition	PTH	TSV	180 nm CMOS ²	TGV	180 nm CMOS		
L_{DC}	[nH]	0.56 ³	2.5	16.5 ³	3.1	210 ³	1.06		
R_{DC}	[mΩ]	-	12	470 ³	-	0.24	2.5		
Q_{max}	[-]	10 ³	33	13	10.5	16 ³	30		
$F_{Q_{max}}$	[MHz]	6 500 ³	90	390	7 000	20 ³	11 800		
FSR	[GHz]	-	-	1.5 ³	1.25	>1	36		
Area	[mm ²]	0.03	0.4	0.8	0.096	2.4	0.029		
Shape	[-]	Rectangle	Solenoid	Rectangle	Octagon	Solenoid	Rectangle		
Special Note	[-]	11 x 13 μm Magnetic Permalloy Patterns	Magnetic VIA	SEI	Coupled	MCI	Intercalated Graphene		
Number of Turns	[-]	1.5	-	6	2	9	3		
L_A	[nH/mm ²]	18.667	6.25	20.625	32.292	87.5	39.68		

¹ - Evaluated by Simulation, ² - Standard General Purpose Technology without additional process steps, ³ - Approximate data

REFERENCES

- [1] E. P. DeBenedictis, "It's time to redefine moore's law again," *Computer*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 72–75, 2017.
- [2] R. R. Tummala, "Moore's law for packaging to replace moore's law for ics," in *2019 Pan Pacific Microelectronics Symposium (Pan Pacific)*, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [3] C. K. Alexander and M. N. O. Sadiku, "Capacitors and inductors," in *Fundamentals of electric circuits*, 5th ed. MC Graw-Hill, 2013, p. 215252.
- [4] T. Xu, J. Sun, H. Wu, H. Li, H. Li, and Z. Tao, "3d mems in-chip solenoid inductor with high inductance density for power mems device," *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 40, no. 11, pp. 1816–1819, 2019.
- [5] L. Peng, Z. Ali, L. Selvaraj, C. S. Cheng, Y. C. Ng, N. A. Yosokumoro, L. Lehmann, P. Rohlf, and M. Wieland, "Silicon-based ultimate miniature magnetic inductors technology for high-efficiency dc-dc conversion," in *2020 32nd International Symposium on Power Semiconductor Devices and ICs (ISPSD)*, 2020, pp. 384–387.
- [6] C.-L. Chen, Y.-C. Hsu, J.-S. Hsieh, C.-H. Tsai, V. C. Y. Chang, A. Roth, E. Soenen, C.-T. Wang, and D. Yu, "Ultra-low-resistance 3d info inductors for integrated voltage regulator applications," in *2016 IEEE International Electron Devices Meeting (IEDM)*, 2016, pp. 35.2.1–35.2.4.
- [7] V. N. Rao Vanukuru, "Enhanced q improvement in rectangular shaped inductors with tapered spirals," in *2018 IEEE MTT-S International Microwave and RF Conference (IMaRC)*, 2018, pp. 1–3.
- [8] Z. Dang, H. Jia, W. Deng, Z. Wang, and B. Chi, "Optimization methods for high inductance-density inductors for high speed integrated circuits," in *2021 IEEE International Conference on Integrated Circuits, Technologies and Applications (ICTA)*, 2021, pp. 243–244.
- [9] D. Sun and X. Li, "The inductance comparison of transmission line and conventional spiral inductor," in *2017 IEEE 5th International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC-Beijing)*, 2017, pp. 1–3.
- [10] C.-L. Chen, Y.-C. Hsu, J.-S. Hsieh, C.-H. Tsai, V. C. Y. Chang, A. Roth, E. Soenen, C.-T. Wang, and D. Yu, "Ultra-low-resistance 3d info inductors for integrated voltage regulator applications," in *2016 IEEE International Electron Devices Meeting (IEDM)*, 2016, pp. 35.2.1–35.2.4.
- [11] P. Zou, Q. Xie, W. Song, Q. Jiang, Y. Lu, and B. Huang, "Powering 5g era computing platforms the road toward integrated power delivery," in *2019 31st International Symposium on Power Semiconductor Devices and ICs (ISPSD)*, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [12] W. J. Lambert, M. J. Hill, K. P. O'Brien, K. Radhakrishnan, and P. Fischer, "Study of thin-film magnetic inductors applied to integrated voltage regulators," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 6208–6220, 2020.
- [13] Y. Ding, X. Fang, R. Wu, Q. Guo, and J. K. O. Sin, "A suspended thick-winding inductor for integrated voltage regulator applications," *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 95–98, 2020.
- [14] Y. Ding, X. Fang, R. Wu, and J. K. O. Sin, "Fan-out-package-embedded coupled inductors for integrated voltage conversion," in *2020 32nd International Symposium on Power Semiconductor Devices and ICs (ISPSD)*, 2020, pp. 356–359.
- [15] Y. Ding, X. Fang, R. Wu, and J. K. O. Sin, "A new fan-out-package-embedded power inductor technology," *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 268–271, 2020.
- [16] P. M. Talekar and V. Pulijala, "Wideband tunable radio frequency integrated circuit inductors integrated with domain-patterned permalloy," *IEEE Magnetics Letters*, vol. 12, pp. 1–5, 2021.
- [17] G. Lv, N. Liao, Y. Ding, X. Fang, F. Bai, J. K. O. Sin, and R. Wu, "A high-efficiency double-side silicon-embedded inductor for integrated dc-dc converter applications," *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, vol. 68, no. 9, pp. 4801–4804, 2021.
- [18] X. Fang, T. H. Mak, Y. Gao, K. M. Lau, P. K. T. Mok, and J. K. O. Sin, "A low substrate loss, monolithically integrated power inductor for compact led drivers," in *2015 IEEE 27th International Symposium on Power Semiconductor Devices & IC's (ISPSD)*, 2015, pp. 53–56.
- [19] C. Schaefer, N. Desai, H. K. Krishnamurthy, X. Liu, K. Z. Ahmed, S. Kim, S. Weng, H. Do, W. J. Lambert, K. Radhakrishnan, K. Ravichandran, J. W. Tschanz, and V. De, "A light-load efficient fully integrated voltage regulator in 14-nm cmos with 2.5-nh package-embedded air-core inductors," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 54, no. 12, pp. 3316–3325, 2019.
- [20] M. Lee, Y. Choi, and J. Kim, "A 500-mhz, 0.76-w/mm power density and 76.2% power efficiency, fully integrated digital buck converter in 65-nm cmos," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 3315–3323, 2016.
- [21] R. Ma, F. Lu, Q. Chen, C. Wang, F. Liu, W. Zou, and A. Wang, "A 2.222.92ghz lc-vco demonstrated with an integrated magnetic-enhanced inductor in 180nm soi cmos," in *2016 IEEE Radio Frequency Integrated Circuits Symposium (RFIC)*, 2016, pp. 110–113.
- [22] N. Tang, W. Hong, B. Nguyen, Z. Zhou, J.-H. Kim, and D. Heo, "Fully integrated switched-inductor-capacitor voltage regulator with 0.82-a/mm2 peak current density and 78% peak power efficiency," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 56, no. 6, pp. 1805–1815, 2021.
- [23] A. Novello, G. Atzeni, J. Knzli, G. Cristiano, M. Coustans, and T. Jang, "A 1.25-ghz fully integrated dc-dc converter using electromagnetically coupled class-d lc oscillators," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 56, no. 12, pp. 3639–3654, 2021.
- [24] Y. Sun, W. Deng, and B. Chi, "A fom of -191 db, 4.4-ghz lc-vco integrating an 8-shaped inductor with an orthogonal-coupled tail-filtering inductor," in *2020 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, 2020, pp. 1–4.
- [25] H. T. Le, Y. Nour, Z. Pavlovic, C. O'Mathna, A. Knott, F. Jensen, A. Han, S. Kulkarni, and Z. Ouyang, "High-q three-dimensional microfabricated magnetic-core toroidal inductors for power supplies in package," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 74–85, 2019.
- [26] C. Alvarez, S. Suresh, M. Swaminathan, R. Tummala, D. Sasaki, K. Watanabe, R. Nagatsuka, C. Ping Lin, T. Wada, and N. Watanabe, "Design and demonstration of single and coupled embedded toroidal inductors for 48v to 1v integrated voltage regulators," in *2020 IEEE 70th Electronic Components and Technology Conference (ECTC)*, 2020, pp. 405–413.
- [27] P. Murali, V. Avula, M. Ahmed, M. D. Losego, M. Swaminathan, C. Alvarez, Y. Oishi, T. Uemura, R. Nagatsuka, and N. Watanabe, "Fabrication and characterization of package embedded inductors for integrated voltage regulators," in *2022 IEEE 72nd Electronic Components and Technology Conference (ECTC)*, 2022, pp. 301–305.
- [28] J. Onohara, F. Takagi, T. Kizu, K. Imayoshi, H. Nomura, and H. Yun, "Development of the integrated passive device using through-glass-via substrate," in *2018 International Conference on Electronics Packaging and iMAPS All Asia Conference (ICEP-IAAC)*, 2018, pp. 19–22.
- [29] H. K. Krishnamurthy, V. Vaidya, P. Kumar, R. Jain, S. Weng, S. T. Kim, G. E. Matthew, N. Desai, X. Liu, K. Ravichandran, J. W. Tschanz, and V. De, "A digitally controlled fully integrated voltage regulator with on-die solenoid inductor with planar magnetic core in 14-nm tri-gate cmos," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 8–19, 2018.
- [30] Y. He, L. Wang, Y. Wang, H. Zhang, Z. Zhong, and F. Bai, "On-chip solenoid power inductors with nanogranular magnetic cores," in *2016 IEEE International Nanoelectronics Conference (INEC)*, 2016, pp. 1–2.
- [31] N. Wang, B. B. Doris, A. B. Shehata, E. J. O'Sullivan, S. L. Brown, S. Rosnagel, J. Ott, L. Gignac, M. Massouras, L. T. Romankiw, and H. L. Deligianni, "High-q magnetic inductors for high efficiency on-chip power conversion," in *2016 IEEE International Electron Devices Meeting (IEDM)*, 2016, pp. 35.3.1–35.3.4.
- [32] K. Bharath, K. Radhakrishnan, M. J. Hill, P. Chatterjee, H. Hariri, S. Venkataraman, H. T. Do, L. Wojewoda, and S. Srinivasan, "Integrated voltage regulator efficiency improvement using coaxial magnetic composite core inductors," in *2021 IEEE 71st Electronic Components and Technology Conference (ECTC)*, 2021, pp. 1286–1292.
- [33] M. Sankarasubramanian, K. Radhakrishnan, Y. Min, W. Lambert, M. J. Hill, A. Dani, R. Mesch, L. Wojewoda, J. Chavarria, and A. Augustine, "Magnetic inductor arrays for intel fully integrated voltage regulator (fivr) on 10th generation intel core socs," in *2020 IEEE 70th Electronic Components and Technology Conference (ECTC)*, 2020, pp. 399–404.
- [34] A. Roth, C. Zhou, M. Wong, E. Soenen, T.-C. Huang, P. Ranucci, Y.-C. Hsu, H.-C. Lin, C. Kuo, M.-J. Wang, S.-Y. Yang, J. R. Chu, T.-Y. Yeh, K. C. Ting, A. L. S. Loke, S. Rusu, M. Chen, F. Y. H. Lee, K. Zhang, and A. Kalnitsky, "Heterogeneous power delivery for 7nm high-performance chiplet-based processors using integrated passive device and in-package voltage regulator," in *2020 IEEE Symposium on VLSI Technology*, 2020, pp. 1–2.
- [35] S. L. Selvaraj, M. Haug, C. S. Cheng, D. Dinulovic, L. Peng, K. E. Shafey, Z. Ali, M. Shousha, Y. C. Ng, N. Aziz Yosokumoro, L. Lehmann, and M. Wieland, "On-chip thin film inductor for high frequency dc-dc power conversion applications," in *2020 IEEE Applied*

- Power Electronics Conference and Exposition (APEC)*, 2020, pp. 176–180.
- [36] N. Sturcken, R. Davies, H. Wu, M. Lekas, K. Shepard, K. W. Cheng, C. C. Chen, Y. S. Su, C. Y. Tsai, K. D. Wu, J. Y. Wu, Y. C. Wang, K. C. Liu, C. C. Hsu, C. L. Chang, W. C. Hua, and A. Kalnitsky, "Magnetic thin-film inductors for monolithic integration with cmos," in *2015 IEEE International Electron Devices Meeting (IEDM)*, 2015, pp. 11.4.1–11.4.4.
- [37] W. Kern, "Chapter 1 - overview and evolution of silicon wafer cleaning technology," in *Handbook of Silicon Wafer Cleaning Technology (Third Edition)*, 3rd ed., K. A. Reinhardt and W. Kern, Eds. William Andrew Publishing, 2018, pp. 3–85. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780323510844000010>
- [38] J.-H. Cheng, W. Wong, X.-N. Wang, Z. Gan, Y. Yue, L. Liu, and L. Zhong, "Novel rf cmos symmetric inductor with stacked multi layer/finger structure," in *2014 12th IEEE International Conference on Solid-State and Integrated Circuit Technology (ICSICT)*, 2014, pp. 1–3.
- [39] X. Xu, P. Li, M. Cai, and B. Han, "Design of novel high- q -factor multipath stacked on-chip spiral inductors," *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, vol. 59, no. 8, pp. 2011–2018, 2012.
- [40] J. Lopez-Villegas, J. Samitier, C. Cane, P. Losantos, and J. Bausells, "Improvement of the quality factor of rf integrated inductors by layout optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 76–83, 2000.
- [41] V. N. R. Vanukuru and A. Chakravorty, "Series stacked multipath inductor with high self resonant frequency," *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, vol. 62, no. 3, pp. 1058–1062, 2015.
- [42] S.-M. Yim, T. Chen, and K. O, "The effects of a ground shield on the characteristics and performance of spiral inductors," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 237–244, 2002.
- [43] A. S. Royet, J. C. Barb, O. Valorge, L. Rmy, and I. Constant, "Experimental and simulation results on si integrated inductor efficiency for smart rf-ics," in *2014 21st IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Circuits and Systems (ICECS)*, 2014, pp. 367–370.
- [44] T. Barwicz, R. L. Bruce, and S. Kamlapurkar, "Far back end of the line stack encapsulation," U.S. Patent 8932956, January, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.freepatentsonline.com/8932956.html>
- [45] G. K. Celler and S. Cristoloveanu, "Frontiers of silicon-on-insulator," *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 93, no. 9, pp. 4955–4978, May 2003. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1558223>
- [46] V. N. R. Vanukuru and A. Chakravorty, "Integrated layout optimized high- g inductors on high-resistivity soi substrates for rf front-end modules," in *2014 International Conference on Signal Processing and Communications (SPCOM)*, 2014, pp. 1–5.
- [47] D. Yu, Z. Huang, Z. Xiao, L. Yang, and M. Xiang, "Embedded si fan out: A low cost wafer level packaging technology without molding and de-bonding processes," in *2017 IEEE 67th Electronic Components and Technology Conference (ECTC)*, 2017, pp. 28–34.
- [48] D. S. Gardner, G. Schrom, P. Hazucha, F. Paillet, T. Karnik, S. Borkar, J. Saulters, J. Owens, and J. Wetzel, "Integrated on-chip inductors with magnetic films," in *2006 International Electron Devices Meeting*, 2006, pp. 1–4.
- [49] "Interconnect," in *2009 International Technology Roadmap for Semiconductors (ITRS)*. Semiconductor Industry Association, 2009, pp. 4–5.
- [50] R. Wu and J. K. O. Sin, "A novel silicon-embedded coreless inductor for high-frequency power management applications," *IEEE Electron Device Letters*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 60–62, 2011.
- [51] R. Wu, N. Liao, X. Fang, and J. K. O. Sin, "A novel double-side silicon-embedded transformer for 10-mhz, 1-kv-isolation, compact power transfer applications," *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, vol. 63, no. 11, pp. 4542–4545, 2016.
- [52] J. Yu, D. Kim, I. Han, and J. Yook, "Demonstration of substrate embedded ni-zn ferrite core solenoid inductors using a photosensitive glass substrate," in *2022 IEEE 72nd Electronic Components and Technology Conference (ECTC)*, 2022, pp. 296–300.
- [53] Y. Ding, X. Fang, R. Wu, Q. Guo, and J. K. O. Sin, "A silicon molded metal transfer process for on-chip suspended power inductors," in *2019 20th International Conference on Solid-State Sensors, Actuators and Microsystems & Eurosensors XXXIII (TRANSDUCERS & EUROSENSORS XXXIII)*, 2019, pp. 142–145.
- [54] A. S. Wartenberg, *RF Measurements of Die and Packages*. Artech House, 2002.
- [55] J. I. Bahl, *Lumped Elements for RF and Microwave Circuits*. Artech House, 2003.
- [56] J.-H. Cho, D.-K. Kim, H.-H. Bae, Y.-J. Lee, S.-T. Koh, Y. Choo, J.-S. Paek, and H.-S. Kim, "A fully integrated multi-phase buck converter with on-chip capacitor dynamic re-allocation and fine-grained phase-shedding techniques," *IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits*, pp. 1–13, 2022.
- [57] J.-J. Lee, S.-H. Yang, B. Muniandi, M.-W. Chien, K.-H. Chen, Y.-H. Lin, S.-R. Lin, and T.-Y. Tsai, "Multiphase active energy recycling technique for overshoot voltage reduction in internet-of-things applications," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 58–67, 2021.
- [58] S. Reddy K, N. Kumar Ch, S. Ch, A. D, S. Rebelli, and L. Raju Thoutam, "Design of high quality factor symmetrical differential inductor using intercalated-graphene," in *2022 2nd International Conference on Intelligent Technologies (CONIT)*, 2022, pp. 1–4.